

First record of *Zelus renardii* Kolenati, 1857 (Hemiptera: Heteroptera: Reduviidae: Harpactorinae) in Bulgaria

Torsten van der Heyden

Immenweide 83, 22523 Hamburg, Germany.

E-mail: tmvdh@web.de ORCID iD: 0000-0003-4138-7160

ABSTRACT: The first record of *Zelus renardii* Kolenati, 1857 (Hemiptera: Heteroptera: Reduviidae: Harpactorinae) for Bulgaria is reported. This record extends the known European distribution of the species.

KEYWORDS: *Zelus renardii*, first record, distribution, Bulgaria, Mediterranean Region.

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Zelus renardii Kolenati, 1857 (Hemiptera: Heteroptera: Reduviidae: Harpactorinae) is a highly invasive Nearctic assassin bug which has colonized several European countries. Recently, Kment & van der Heyden (2022) published a list of the known distribution of *Z. renardii* in Europe. of the specimen were uploaded to the online database iNaturalist (Ivanov, 2022). This record from Bulgaria extends the known European distribution of *Z. renardii* from the eastern Mediterranean Region northeastward.

In addition to that list, the first record of *Z. renardii* in Bulgaria can be reported: On 01.10.2022, a female specimen was found and photographed by Galin Ivanov in the city of Burgas, located at the Burgas Bay on the western coast of the Black Sea (Fig. 1). Several photographs

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Figure 1. *Zelus renardii* Kolenati, 1857, female (with prey), Burgas, Bulgaria, 01.10.2022. (Photo: Galin Ivanov).